

Feeding Management during Transition Period

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Introduction

The peri-parturient or transition period is defined as 21 days prior to and 21 days after calving as the cow transitions from pregnant non-lactating state to non-pregnant lactating state. It is considered as critical physiological stage in the dairy cattle production cycle. This stage is characterized by dramatic physiological and metabolic adaptations, and the cow is at the highest risk of succumbing to health disorder during this time (Loor *et al.*, 2013). Diseases that result from disordered homeostatic change reflect disorders in homeostasis, in other words, these are failures to adapt that result in shortages of nutrients that are vital for existence. These conditions are often inter-related and include hypocalcemia and downer cows, hypomagnesaemia, ketosis and fatty liver, udder oedema, abomasal displacement, metritis, poor fertility and poor production.

Mechanism of the Transition Period

With the signs of gestation, the dry matter intake (DMI) of dairy cow decreases and is at its lowest near parturition. The score of body condition (BCS) parallels the DMI, but the aim should be not to lose more than one BCS after calving. The higher demand for energy and nutrients for the synthesis of colostrum and milk coupled with the decline in feed intake forces the transition cows to undergo negative energy balance (NEB) and micronutrient deficiencies. The NEB stimulates cows to mobilize body fat in the form of non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA) and subsequent accumulation of beta-hydroxybutyric acid (BHBA) in the blood (Wankhade, 2017). At

the same time, with the growth of the fetus, the nutrient requirement increases and is at their peak before parturition, as well as immediately after parturition. The milk production reaches its peak in about 5-8 weeks postpartum, while the diet consumption peaks at 10-14 weeks postpartum. So, dairy cows will typically suffer in a 6-8 weeks period of NEB during the postpartum period. Concurrently, mammary energy requirements at 4 days postpartum are more than three times that of the uterus, by a simultaneous increase in requirement of metabolizable protein, particularly of methionine and lysine. The incidences of metabolic and infectious diseases are higher mostly immediately after calving. The body reserves mobilization, especially fat and

protein; and hepatic gluconeogenesis occurs immediately after parturition leading to increased levels of BHBA and NEFA which act as a gateway for several metabolic diseases (Bakshi, 2017).

Transition period feeding

Feeding during transition phase will determine both the milk production in the ensuing lactation as well as the reproductive efficiency of the animal. Transition period feeding is a management strategy of the dairy cows that ensures a smooth and healthy progression from the late stages of pregnancy to lactation which is also known as “lead feeding”. From a rumen microbiota point of view, nutrition-induced changes during the transition period could play a vital role in providing optimal amounts of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), propionate in particular, to help alleviate the demands of the mammary gland for glucose and energy. Cows should be provided with a transition feeding program 3 weeks before calving and it must be ensured that they have been provided calcium and the rumen is adapting to higher levels of grain. The absence of knowledge and skill among the farmers during this period exacerbates the cow's situation. The metabolic adaptations, metabolic changes and nutritional-management strategies can ease the transition feeding period. Considerable improvement can be achieved in milk production by providing all the nutrients in the appropriate quantity, quality and proportions. To get the maximum output from dairy cows, proper attention to the feeding of a pregnant dry cow is necessary (Bakshi, 2017). Changing to a shorter dry period, and reducing postpartum energy demands and fluxes in circulating metabolites may be a first step in offering practical solutions (Shoshani *et al.*, 2014).

Nutritional science behind Transition Period Feeding and Management

Major shifts in metabolic change and hormones occur during the transition period as

the fetus is rapidly growing. So, by feeding management, optimal dietary requirements can be fulfilled. During the transition period, dairy cows go through large metabolic adaptations in glucose, fatty acid and mineral metabolism. If they are provided, the lactation is supported and metabolic dysfunction can be avoided (Overton, 2004). The handling of mineral metabolism with anionic salts is an important aspect of transition period feeding. The mobilization and utilization of calcium reduce the risk of milk fever. The feeding of supplementary grain prepares the cow's rumen for the high level of grain in the post calving ration. For the critical phase of late pregnancy and fetal development, the bypass protein helps to meet the increased demand for protein. During the transition period feeding, restricting access to lush green pasture is vital, because it will avoid high levels of potassium in the diet which can enhance the risk of milk fever. Providing *ad lib* cereal hay during the transition period is also important because it promotes rumination and gut fill as well as displays a mineral profile which reduces milk fever risk and promotes milk production in the ensuing lactation. The low quality of desired nutritious ration causes nutritional imbalances and it is reflected by reduced appetite and ingestion and is in turn responsible for depressed performance specifically during the transition period (Bakshi, 2017). The reproductive efficiency of the animal is also determined by the appropriate feeding during the pregnancy and post-pregnancy period.

Changes during the transition period:

The changes that occur during the peri-parturient period are as follows:

- Large increase in glucose demand by the fetus and then mammary gland
- Dramatic changes in hormone levels
- Changes in feed intake
- Negative energy balance
- Negative protein balance
- Hypocalcemia
- Immunosuppression

Diagrammatic representation of major changes during transition period in dairy cattle in negative energy balance (Singh, A., 2021)

Metabolic Changes

The major physiological changes that occur during this critical period are:

- DMI decreases around parturition and body condition score (BCS) also changes
- Sudden increase in nutrients requirement that is needed for the fetus growth and onset of milk production

- Metabolic adaptations required for meeting the nutrient requirements

Infectious diseases and metabolic disorders

The nutrient deficiencies and excesses are responsible for metabolic and infectious diseases, and thus for animal welfare impairment, and overall may result in poor efficiency and income for the farm. The high incidence of metabolic and infectious diseases is responsible for the high occurrence of inflammatory conditions in the transition period (mostly after calving). In particular, in high-yielding cows, this occurs during the transition period and the inadequate increase of DMI can be an important causal factor. Retained placenta, metritis and endometritis are the diseases of immune function in the transition period, starting at least 2 weeks before calving. However, low DMI also is a consequence of health disorders that induce inflammatory conditions (such as metritis, mastitis, lameness, etc.) through the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Dairy cows with the worst inflammatory index appear to be affected by NEB and increased levels of β -hydroxy butyric acid (BHBA). If animals are not fed properly during the transition period, they face the negative energy balance (NEB). The NEB makes the animal, particularly the high yielding dairy cows, susceptible to various metabolic and infectious diseases like clinical ketosis, milk fever, mastitis and metritis. This leads to a great economic loss for the dairy industry (Nain, 2021).

Fig. Milk fever

Fig. Ketosis

Feeding management

- The diet should be offered as TMR in order to avoid the selective intake of feedstuffs, effective utilization of nutrients and to save labour thereby economizing production
- The feed intake is correlated with ambient temperature. The heat associated with digestion of feed, peaks about 3-4 h after feeding. By feeding cows in early morning (5-6 a.m.), the heat of digestion peaks at 8-9 a.m., and allows the cow to dissipate some of that heat before the day gets hot.
- In addition, frequent small meals (3-4 times a day) result in less heat generation than fewer, but larger meals
- Water is the most important nutrient for the cow. DMI and milk yield depend on free access to fresh, clean and cool water. Water should be provided within 15 m area of the feed manger. About 5 litres of water is required per kg of milk produced. Decrease in water intake by 40% results in 16-24% decline in DMI and considerable decline in milk yield
- Feed additives should be used for optimizing health and to maximize the profitability from the dairy farming. Many feed additives have now become routine components of transition cow rations. These aim at combining beneficial effects on energy metabolism with stimulatory action on the liver and immune system

- The diet of a high-yielding cow contains about 50% concentrate mixture containing 40-50% cereal grains result in less salivation and thereby reducing rumen buffering capacity. As rumen pH drops to near 6, fibre digestion is sharply reduced, the animal goes off feed, and DMI is reduced. The dietary buffers such as sodium bicarbonate, magnesium oxide, calcium carbonate, etc. can be used to neutralize the acidity in the rumen. Addition of dietary buffers at the rate of 1.5% in the high concentrate (cereal based) ration can increase DMI, milk yield and its fat content. Feeding a properly balanced ration containing high-quality forage like alfalfa, which has a high buffering capacity, can minimize the need for buffers

Conclusion

Nutritional management plays an important role during the transition period (3 weeks on either side of the parturition) in the high-yielding cows. The imbalances in ration and nutrition, like the low quality of desired nutritious rations, reduced appetite and low intake are responsible for decreased performance, specifically during the transition period. Also, factors such as the lack of knowledge and skill of farmers in feeding management during the transition period exacerbate the situation in most of the developing countries. Majority of the farmers boost up the feeding of animals only after parturition, but they should be advised to use the proper type of feeding management required during the transition period.

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